

REVIEW ON GREEN FLAME-RETARDANT MATERIALS FOR TEXTILE FINISHING

Tanuja Kohli

Research Scholar, Department of Textile and Apparel Designing,
College of Community and Applied Sciences, Maharana Pratap University of Agriculture and
Technology, Udaipur 313001, India

Meenu Srivastava

Professor, Department of Textile and Apparel Designing, College of Community and Applied
Sciences, Maharana Pratap University of Agriculture and Technology, Udaipur 313001, India

C. Prakash

Director, Department of Handloom and Textile Technology,
IIHT, Fulia, Ministry of Textiles, Govt. of India, Shantipur, Nadia-West Bengal, India

*Corresponding author email: tanujakohli336@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Development of flame-retardant properties of textiles is becoming more important with the increasing uses of flammable polymers in household and industrial sectors. CTIF statistics reported deaths of 37,000 human beings per year due to fire incidents in 31 countries. Commercially used synthetic fire-retardant chemicals are reported as toxic, required in large quantities, and include cumbersome treatment processes. Therefore, getting an eco-friendly, cheap, widely available flame-retardant material is a big challenge and unmet need. In this connection, plant extracts have been popularly explored for making functional textiles to impart functionalities like protection against fire. This study is a brief review of research and developments in the field of eco-friendly flame-retardant textile finishes. It focuses mainly on currently available flame retardant solutions for different kinds of textiles, modes of action, types of flame retardant fibers, and flame retardant additives and treatments.

Keywords: Bio-Based, Eco-Friendly, Fire Retardant, Sustainable, Textile Finishes.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Natural fibre-forming polymers like cellulose and protein, as well as a wide range of synthetic polymers like *polyester*, *polyolefin*, *polylactide*, *polyamides*, *polyaramids*, *polyether ketones*, *polyacrylonitrile*, and cellulose acetate, are used to make textiles due to their superior fibre-forming abilities. However, they all share one same issue the majority of them are combustible in typical environmental conditions and constitute a substantial fire risk in case of fire disaster. Given that these organic polymers are a rich supply of hydrocarbons, they provide for a great fuel source while burning. In reference to this, "flame retardant textiles" refers to fabrics or materials made of fibres that slow down or stop the spread of fire [1].

Different types of textiles, both natural and manufactured, have benefited from the use of phosphorus and/or nitrogen-based, organic, inorganic, and halogenated flame retardants to provide fire resistance. However, due to their severe toxicity for both humans and animals, several compounds, such as *polychlorinated biphenyls*, *decabromodiphenyl*, or *pentabromodiphenyl* ethers have recently been outlawed in the USA and EU [2]. Additionally flame-retardant such as N-alkyl *phosphopropionamide* derivatives and *Tetrakis phosphonium* salt, which are based on formulations of phosphorous, nitrogen, and halogen composition have seen extensive commercial usage. Nevertheless, when such formulations are used on textiles, the tensile strength and tear strength of the fabric are dramatically diminished, in addition to that cloth appears coarser. This mostly occurred because high-temperature procedures were involved in the application of the aforementioned formulations along with an acidic environment. Although the method works well for various fibre types, it has the drawbacks of being poisonous, dangerous, and expensive. Since the year 2000, there has been a rise in global awareness of sustainable eco-friendly green textile chemicals, auxiliaries, and textile products, raising some serious concerns about the environmental friendliness, toxicity, and sustainability of various traditional flame-retardant compounds [3]. People have recently become more conscious of the harmfulness of chemicals and their effects on the environment, as well as the possible risks that may be involved [4].

When aiming for a "greener" approach, it must be considered that existing FRs should be replaced with similar products that exhibit minimal environmental effect and toxicity. But there are a few prerequisites that this kind of treatment must meet; the application of new products must be at least as simple as that of the flame retardant they are replacing, and they must not produce formaldehyde while being applied to the fabric or even when in use. Furthermore, it's essential that the new product preserves the general characteristics of the processed textile, including its soft touch (or "hand"), durability, air permeability, dyeability, aesthetics, and wearability. Lastly, the substitute flame retardant should cost as much as or even less than the one it replaces [5]. In this direction, present study is a review of work done by different investigators in the field of fire-retardant finishing compounds for textile materials, its effect on the environment and sustainable outcome of emerging scenario due to toxicity of finishing treatments.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Mode of action of flame-retardant agents

In the combustion cycle, polymer chains begin to shatter into smaller fragments when heated to a temperature greater than or equal to T_p (pyrolysis temperature) or T_c (combustion temperature). Some of these fragments may be potentially flammable compounds. Further breakdown of these combustible materials results in the production of hydroxyl (OH) and hydrogen (H) radicals, which react with oxygen to produce heat and light.

The resulting heat may be discharged into the atmosphere or it may feed right back into the burning cycle, causing the polymer to decompose even further. Up until the entire polymer has been burned, the burning process, which is a feedback loop, will continue. This feedback mechanism may be disrupted by the presence of flame-retardant chemicals or by the absence of oxygen [6]. For flame retardant action on certain textiles to stop or diminish flame propagation during the burning of fibre polymers, flame retardants function to interrupt the self-sustaining polymer combustion cycle. This extinguishes the flame or reduces the burning rate in a variety of conceivable methods [7]. Flame retardants can be divided into two categories based on how they work: gas-phase action and condensed-phase activity.

Gas-phase action: The development of reactive species during burning is a feature of gas-phase action. Flame retardants with halogen [8] and phosphorus bases mostly display this behaviour [9-10]. The reactive species might be phosphorus derivatives or halogen radicals (X), which function as scavengers of free radicals in the vapor phase. By drawing hydrogen from the flame retardant (RX) or the polymer (PH), halogen-based flame retardants have the potential to produce halogen radical, which can then result in hydrogen halide (HX). The burning cycle may be disrupted by the hydrogen halide's potential to further react with the hydrogen and hydroxyl radicals (reactions A and B, respectively) produced by the breakdown of polymers.

Condensed phase action: The creation of a shield between the pyrolyzing polymer and the heat source describes condensed phase activity. When a polymer is thermally decomposed, the flame-retardant ingredient reacts with the polymer to generate this protective barrier/char. The polymer decomposes at lower temperatures as a result of the catalytic interaction between the flame-retardant additive and the polymer. Flame retardants work by altering the pyrolytic pathways of heat degradation or by potentially slowing down the development of flammable materials. A significant number of water molecules are produced when phosphorus acidic species combine with hydroxyl-containing polymers like cellulose in certain cases, the phosphorus compounds break down to create *polyphosphoric acid*, which coats the surface of dissolving polymers to act as a heat barrier [11-12-13]. When external nitrogen alterations like urea, guanidine, and melamine are present, the condensed phase activity of phosphorus flame retardants might be further boosted (P-N Synergism). Probable chemical interaction between degraded nitrogen additive products and phosphorus compounds to generate a protective layer on the surface of char was considered to be the cause of the improved activity of phosphorus flame retardant [14].

A low heat permeable char layer, which is generated during burning of a flame-retardant cloth, can stop the transfer of heat and oxygen. During the course of the procedure, non-flammable gasses like CO₂ and H₂O help to reduce the assimilation of heat energy by diluting the proportion of the combustible gasses. Theoretically, in flame-retardant fabrics' non-flammable gases may withstand flames by working concurrently in condensed and gaseous phases while being burned [15,16,17,18].

2.2 Types of flame-retardant fibers

A fibre is more flammable when it has lower T_c values and a higher flame temperature [6,19]. The most crucial element affecting the textile materials' flammability is their polymer foundation. Designing an efficient flame retardant system requires an understanding of the thermal behaviour of polymers both by themselves and in the presence of additives. When polymers are exposed to high temperatures, several physical and chemical changes may occur that are connected to the polymer's physical and chemical structure.

Thermoplastics undergo physical changes like Tg and Tm, which are significant and may potentially affect the polymers' flammability [6,20].

It has been discovered that due to the loose structure, garments made from coarse yarns burn more readily than those made from fine yarn. The ignition time at the knotted textiles was influenced by yarn count and twist factor. The ignition times drop as the number of yarns increases [21]. Additionally, flame-resistant textiles can be made from materials including Nomex, Kevlar, wool, *Trevira* CS, modacrylics, melamine fibers, and polyvinyl chloride that are naturally flame-resistant [22,23].

Manufacturing companies can create flame-resistant textiles by applying surface treatments of various chemistries or by adding fire-retardant additives to polymer bulk prior to fiber spinning. Additionally, the flammability of materials can be significantly influenced by fabric blends. Fabric blends produced from two separate fibrous polymers may exhibit flammability traits that are very dissimilar from those displayed by the blend's individual components. For instance, cotton fabrics are more flammable than polyester fabrics, but mixed polyester/cotton blends burn more quickly. This is due to the "scaffolding" effect, in which the polyester fibers provide as a support for the burned cotton in the blend. As opposed to 100% polyester garments, the melting polyester in the blend continues to burn (wicking effect). The weight and weave pattern of the fabric have only a little impact on the flammability and thermal shrinkage, which are mainly influenced by the thermal stability of the component fibers [24,25].

One of the most popular polymers for creating flame-resistant fabrics today is aromatic polyamides, also known as aramids, which were initially discovered in the 1960s. These fibres are used to create military apparel and accessories, industrial worker uniforms, firefighters' uniforms, and other garments [26,27].

Fig. 1 Inherently flame retardant polymers

Basofil Fibres LLC, Enka, NC produces melamine fibres that can withstand high temperatures and sell them under the brand name *Basofil*® Fibre (TNC Global Inc, 2010). They often focus on the markets for hot gas filtration and safety and protective apparel and have high LOI values. Melamine fibres are produced using synthetic fiber-forming polymers that contain at least 50% by weight of a cross-linked melamine polymer. For comparable qualities, the price of melamine fibre is cheap [28]. An organic fibre with great heat resistance and a nice hand is *polybenzimidazole* (PBI). It doesn't melt or drop, and it doesn't burn in the air. Also, PBI is a great fibre for fire-blocking end applications such safety and protective apparel and flame retardant textiles because to its high LOI, outstanding chemical resistance, and good moisture recovery [29]. Modacrylic and polyvinyl chloride-based halogenated fibres have specific applications in the manufacture of industrial and residential furnishings that require strong chemical resistance and fire protection. Glass fibres are constructed from the same inorganic amorphous polymer that is used to create barrier textiles for high-temperature filtration, defense-related uses, and furniture.

Fibres made of *polyphenylene sulfide* are renowned for their good chemical resistance and mild thermal resistance. *Benzobisoxazole poly-phenylene* is a brand-new, exceptionally well organic fibre. It has about double the tensile strength of typical para-aramid fibres and exceptional thermal characteristics. It is a great choice for composite reinforcement due to its high modulus. PBO has a significantly higher LOI value than meta aramid fibres—more than twice as high [1].

2.3 Flame retardant additives and treatments

To improve the fire retardant quality of fabrics used in French theatres, Gay-Lussac proposed a combination of ammonium phosphate, ammonium chloride, and borax in 1820 [30]. Some synthetic fibres looked to have inherent fire resistance during the twentieth century for example, Nomex®, the first *polyaramide*, was marketed in 1961. It was discovered that compounds with phosphorous as a main ingredient worked well as flame retardants for cellulosic materials. Phosphorous molecules are precursors of acids, and these acids take part in the dehydration that leads to the production of char. Numerous researchers have also asserted that the inclusion of nitrogenous compounds enhances flame retardancy [31]. Also, it has been reported that due to their synergistic impact, nitrogenous chemicals and phosphorus-based flame retardants are the most effective. As a result, phosphorous, nitrogen, and halogen-based flame retardants such *tetrakis* phosphonium salt and *Nalkyl phosphopropionamide* derivatives predominate in commercial usage. As these formulations are applied in an acidic environment, it has been discovered that they diminish the tensile strength of cloth. In addition, because so many chemicals and a high-temperature curing method are used, treatment is poisonous, risky, costly, and time-consuming [32].

A British patent issued to Obadiah WYLD in 1735 contains an early description of flame-resistant cellulosic materials. This patent included instructions for using alum, borax, and vitriol to stop paper, pulp, or textiles from catching fire [33]. Additionally, great progress was achieved in creating a finish for linen and jute materials that resists flames. In this case, ammonium phosphate, ammonium chloride, and borax were combined to provide the desired flame resistance [34]. Commercially available *N-methylol dimethylphosphonopropionamide* (*Pyrovatex* CP) systems have been used to increase the flame resistance of textiles to comply with fire safety norms [35]. Nevertheless, these organophosphorus-based FR products have the potential to leak formaldehyde both during manufacturing and even after they have been put into use. These are harmful to both people and the surroundings [32]. Studies to partially or entirely replace such products with functional compounds that are efficient and sustainable have been inspired by recent knowledge of formaldehyde toxicity.

There has been a broad study of the effects of non-durable, semi-durable, and durable flame retardants [36,37]. The most significant class of flame retardants are those that include phosphorus and work as char promoters in condensed phase in the majority of polymer substrates. In terms of the toxicity of the primary flame-retardant compounds and the risks associated with application and end use, toxicological dangers of flame retardants are frequently questioned. They looked into frequently used cellulosic flame retardants and noted that substances like antimony oxide and tris (*aziridinyl*) phosphine oxide (APO) can be completely hazardous [38].

Urea with phosphoric acid method is superior to the Stannate and Phosphate Step method for a durable flame-retardant finish to cellulosic fabrics in terms of higher flame resistance, better tensile properties, and reduced stiffness character [39]. In order to give some vapor-phase flame retardant effect, ammonium bromide can also be employed in conjunction with ammonium phosphates. This is especially useful for blends [40,41].

Some ammonium phosphate formulations additionally contain ammonium sulfamate or sulphate [42]. Additionally, efforts have been made to use these organic salts to create long-lasting coatings on cellulose [43,44]. Additional examples of phosphates used for non-durable cotton treatment are monoguanidine dihydrogen phosphates and diguanidine hydrogen phosphate [45]. Semi-durable coatings have been created using flame retardants such *Flovan*® CGN (Ciba), *Flammentin*® FMB (Thor Specialties), and *Pyrovatim*® PBS [42]. Although these flame-retardant treatments may withstand varying degrees of water absorption or leaching, they wash poorly. These inorganic phosphate coatings are not alkaline washing conditions resistant. When ammonium cations chemically bond with phosphoric acid groups and neutralize them, the finish can become quite resistant to water washing. When treating cellulose-based textiles using DMPMP (3-(*dimethylphosphono*)-*N-methylolpropionamide*), a formaldehyde-based cross-linker, such as melamine formaldehyde, is typically used to provide durable results. Due to the production of formaldehyde fumes, the presence of formaldehyde in DMPMP and the cross-linker causes environmental issues throughout the application process. The subsequent use of the treated cloth may potentially emit formaldehyde. The unique ammonia curing procedure is necessary to fix THPC on cellulosic fabrics, preventing its widespread adoption. The greatest options available now for cellulose-based fabrics' flame-retardant finishing are these chemicals [46]. A long-lasting flame-retardant finishing of cellulose using an oligomeric hydroxyl functional organophosphorus chemical has recently been studied. Cotton and cotton/nylon blends that are flame-resistant have been produced using HFPO [47]. In this investigation, it was discovered that HFPO both increases the quantity of char produced during burning and greatly lowers the temperature at which cotton thermally decomposes. The main issues with many of the present flame retardants include various finishing procedures that contain formaldehyde release, toxicity, and degradation in fabric physiochemical characteristics. Development of sustainable, biomolecule-based, natural, and environment-friendly flame-retardant formulations is required.

2.4 Eco-friendly flame-retardant textile finishes

Natural materials are valuable because of their biodegradability and low toxicity. Also, their ability to accelerate char formation to improve textile flame retardancy, bio-sourced chitosan, deoxyribonucleic acid, proteins, tannins, phytic acid, and vegetable oils have been employed as effective FR products for textiles [5, 48, 49]. Bio-based flame retardants are substances that may be made from biomass, which is referred to as the biological stuff that can be found on earth. It consists of biomolecule-containing plants, animals, and microbes, some of which have essential properties like flame retardancy. By using chemical or biological processes, these compounds can either be employed as-is or transformed into derivatives [50].

Due to the environmental and toxicological risks associated with halogenated flame retardants, four major directives have mandated their replacement since 2005: Evaluation, Authorization, Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), Restriction of Hazardous Substances (RoHS), Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC), and Waste Electric and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) [51].

The acceptability and efficacy of a few biomacromolecules and bio-sourced goods with a particular chemical structure and composition as efficient flame retardants for natural and synthetic textiles have been carefully investigated at the lab-scale level during the last five to ten years. For creating flame retardant finishing treatments for various fibers and textiles, various proteins (such as whey proteins, caseins, and *hydrophobins*), nucleic acids, and extracts from natural sources, including wastes and crops, have been chosen and utilized.

It was discovered that these biomacromolecules and bio-sourced products, which typically contain key elements (such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur), can be applied to textiles with ease using conventional impregnation/exhaustion methods or even the layer-by-layer technique. Furthermore, these "green" products are primarily responsible for the formation of a stable protective char (i.e., a carbonaceous residue), as a result of the exposure of the textile substrate to heat flux or flame [5].

According to a research, fire retardants must not be persistent, bio-accumulative, or hazardous to people, other animals, or the ecosystem as a whole to be considered ecologically benign. The chemical must easily degrade in the environment; this is a crucial criterion. Therefore, natural materials are valuable because of their inherent biodegradability and low toxicity [52]. The ability of bio-sourced chitosan, deoxyribonucleic acid, proteins, tannins, phytic acid, and vegetable oils to catalyze the creation of char to increase the flame retardant characteristic of textiles has led to their application as efficient FR products for textiles.

TAPE reported as green, sustainable, and reactive phosphorus-containing FR agent [53]. The substance was created utilizing PA and TA sourced from plants, and NMR analysis was used to determine its chemical composition. TAPE was employed to create tough FR silk textiles. Due to the shielding effect of the created intumescent char, the modified silk materials had improved LOI by over 32.5% and demonstrated self-extinguishing behavior. Additionally, TAPE improved the silk's thermal resilience and considerably reduced its ability to produce smoke and heat.

Banana pseudo stem sap (BPS), an environmentally benign natural by-product derived from the extraction of fibers from the banana pseudo stem, was used to give lignocellulosic jute textiles flame retardancy. The treated jute textiles demonstrated much greater flame resistance, displayed no flame, and quickly self-extinguished. The method of imparting flame retardancy to jute textiles has been suggested based on thermal degradation, pyrolysis, and dehydration experiments, as well as the study of the chemical composition of the flame-retardant finish generated from the BPS. The imparted finish was found to be semi-durable in soap wash and did not significantly reduce the fabric's tensile and tear strength [49].

The green natural product spinach leaf juice (SJ), which is made from spinach leaves, was used to give cellulosic textiles flame-retardant properties [54]. The limiting oxygen index (LOI), horizontal and vertical flammability, and radiant heat testing were used to analyze the flame retardant qualities of the control and treated textiles. In comparison to control textiles, the investigation revealed that the treated fabrics exhibited good flame retardant properties.

For improving the thermal stability and flame retardant qualities of cotton textiles, deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) from herring sperm has been used as a new flame retardant system [55]. The three primary elements that are typically included in an intumescent formulation—phosphate groups, deoxyribose units, and nitrogen-containing bases that may release ammonia—are all present in DNA, making it a potential candidate for intrinsic intumescent flame retardant status. The results of the horizontal flammability tests demonstrate that the DNA-treated cotton materials do not burn at all after two applications of a methane flame for three seconds. Furthermore, no ignition has been noticed when subjected to a 35 Kwm irradiative heat flux. Finally, a treated fabric's LOI value was 28% as contrasted to the untreated fabric's LOI value of 18%.

Citric acid was used to cross-link cotton without formaldehyde by means of sodium hypophosphite (SHP) as a catalyst. Due to *Pyrovatex's (N-methylol dimethylphosphonopropionamide)* [56]. Improved bonding with cotton in the presence of citric acid and catalyst, the fabric's fire resistance was raised. Additionally, phosphorus-based catalyst SHP increases the amount of phosphorus in the system, which further improves fire retardance.

More research has been done to increase flame retardancy and durability, and butane tetra carboxylic acid (BTCA), a formaldehyde-free substitute, has been tested [56]. ISPA is a brand-new intumescent flame retardant that was made utilizing imidazole and SPDPC. With the use of a finishing liquid formula including ISPA, phosphoric acid, and cyanuric acid, cotton fabric was given a flame-retardant finish. According to the LOI test, cotton cloth treated with the best recipe has the least amount of damage, no ongoing burning, and no smoldering [58].

3. Conclusion

Flame-retardant finishing is significant among the numerous functional textile finishes since it directly relates to safeguarding people and other valuable items from fire risks. The most widely used chemical for this purpose is a combination of phosphorous with nitrogenous compounds and antimony with halogen compounds, but environmentally friendly flame retardants like urea and ammonium sulfamate, BTCA-hydroxyalkyl organophosphorus, and SMSN have been developed due to the toxic effects of these compounds on human health and the environment. The creation and application of "bio-based" FR materials such as salmon fish DNA, whey proteins, casein, and *hydrophobins*, as well as DNA from herring sperm, have all been touched by the "Green Chemistry" revolution. Likewise, SJ, a vegetable extract, and BPS, an agricultural residue, both of which are more sustainable and renewable. An important step toward realizing eco-friendly resources is the utilization of increasingly renewable (bio-based) resources. Additionally, there is a need to create environmentally friendly, cost-effective, minimal to no detrimental effects on the mechanical characteristics of fabric, adaptable to cellulosic, lignocellulosic, and protein textiles, and semi-durable to durable green flame retardant chemicals. Numerous research has looked at how natural ingredients may be utilized to enhance the flame-retardant properties of cellulose and synthetic fibres. The bulk of flame-retardant formulations still lack the necessary durability against rainfall and/or soap washing after multiple such breakthroughs, which calls for urgent attention. It is believed that the extraction and use of different plant molecules and other biomolecules for the flame-retardant finishing of textiles would aid in the development of environmentally friendly green textile goods and ensure the much-needed value addition to agricultural waste.

Furthermore, there are no specific standards for eco-friendly fire retardant finishes at present, so in order for a fire retardant finished textile to be certified as an eco-friendly finish, it must first meet the requirements for the fire retardant performances as per the appropriate National and International standards for the intended end uses, and then the requirements for demonstrating its eco friendliness.

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